

1 **Polarity defects are associated with genesis of human disease.**

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7 We describe here recurrent defects in polarity program gene expression associated with the genesis of
8 human disease. In some cases, expression of the single nucleotide variant associated with the disease in
9 human cells resulted in accumulation of polarity defects. Here, we describe the polarity disrupting potential
10 of NOD2 and SOD1.

11 Citations

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